

THEORETICAL FEATURES OF THE STUDY OF THE PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING THE COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF THE PERSONALITY

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Abstract: This article discusses the scientific-theoretical features of studying the problems of personal communication skills formation in the educational process.

Key words: Educational system, communicative skills, theory, scientific analysis, pantomime, communicator.

Introduction.

Decree No. PF-6108 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 "On measures to develop the fields of education and science in the period of new development of Uzbekistan" was signed. This law was prepared on the basis of the analysis of the national experience and world-class achievements in the educational system from an ideological and fundamental point of view, and was aimed at a high general and professional culture, creative and social activity, and the ability to independently achieve the goal in social and political life. It is very valuable because it is aimed at forming a new generation of personnel who have skills and are able to advance and solve future tasks.

The main goal of the reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan is to create a healthy and well-educated generation in our country with high spiritual and moral qualities. To achieve this goal, our country lives in a new era, thinks in a new way, works in new production, social conditions, has modern professional skills regardless of religion, nationality, race, and observes human rights and freedoms in our republic. A democratic legal state and an open civil society are being built, which will ensure the moral renewal of society, the formation of a socially oriented market economy, and integration into the world community. The main goal and driving force of the reforms implemented in the republic is the harmonious development and well-being of a person in all aspects, the creation of conditions and effective mechanisms for the realization of personal interests, and the change of outdated patterns of thinking and social behavior.

Communication is a specific form of human interaction with other people as members of society, social relations of people are realized in communication. One of the necessary requirements for this is flexibility, non-standard, originality of thinking, the ability to find unconventional solutions.

The process of one person's perception of another is a mandatory component of communication and is called Perception. Since a person always communicates as a human being, he is perceived as a human being by another person. According to S. L. Rubinstein, based on the external side of behavior, another person's "reading" means the meaning of his external information. At the same time, the resulting impressions play an important regulatory role in the communication process.

The process of mutual understanding is "complicated" by the phenomenon of reflection. Reflex is an understanding of how an active person is perceived by a communication partner. It is not just knowing or understanding each other, but knowing how the other understood me, the process of mirroring each other, a deep, consistent relationship, the content of which is to recreate the inner world of the partner, and in this inner world, in turn, my inner world. reflects

The student is taught to communicate in a psychologically correct and situational way, to continue communication, to predict the reactions of partners to their actions, to mentally adapt to the emotional tone of the interlocutors, to take and keep the initiative in communication, to overcome psychological barriers in communication, to eliminating external tension, emotionally adapting to the communication situation, "adapting" to the interlocutor psychologically and physically, choosing the rhythm of your behavior with gestures, positions,

Basic approaches to the problem of learning communicative skills in domestic and foreign psychology.

Communication skills and such communication is a multifaceted process necessary to organize relationships between people during joint activities. And in this sense it refers to material phenomena. But during the dialogue, its participants exchange their thoughts, intentions, ideas, experiences, not only their physical actions or products, the results of work recorded in the article. Thus, communication helps to transmit, exchange, coordinate the ideal forms that exist in the form of human representation, feelings, thinking, etc.

Communication functions are different. They can be determined in the comparative analysis of human communication with different partners, in different conditions, on the tools used and on the behavior and spirit of the communication participants. Communication functions such as information-communication, regulatory-communicative and affective-communicative are of particular importance in the system of relations between a person and other people.

The function of information and communicative communication is, in fact, the transmission and reception of information as a specific message. It has two structural elements: the text (the content of the message) and the attitude towards it (the communicator). Changes in the proportion and nature of these components, that is, the text of the messenger and his attitude to it, significantly affect the perception of the message, its level of understanding and acceptance, and therefore the interaction between people may affect the transfer process. The function of information and communicative communication is well represented in G. Lasswell's popular model, where the communicator (the one who transmits the message), the content of the message (which is transmitted), the channel (as it is transmitted), and the receiver (to whom it is transmitted) are divided into structural units. The effectiveness of information transfer can be expressed by the understanding of the transmitted message, its acceptance (rejection), including the freshness and relevance of the recipient's information.

The regulatory and communicative function of communication is aimed at organizing interactions between people, as well as at correcting the individual's own activity or situation. This function is recognized for the participants' intentions, needs, intentions, goals, tasks, intended methods of interaction, and regulation of the process of implementation of planned programs. The affective-communicative function of communication is the process of changing

the situation of people, which can occur with a special (targeted) and binding effect. In the first case, consciousness and emotions change under the influence of infection (the process of conveying an emotional state by other people), suggestion or belief. A person's need to change his situation, talk it out, pour out his soul, etc. through communication, the general mood of a person changes, which is consistent with the information theory of systems. Communication itself can increase and decrease the level of psychological stress.

During communication, there are mechanisms of social feelings, schoolchildren get to know each other better. Sharing impressions, they begin to understand themselves better, learn to understand their advantages and disadvantages. As mentioned above, communication with a real partner can be carried out using various means of communication: language, gestures, facial expressions, pantomimes, etc. The same can be said about gestures: sometimes just one gesture can completely change the meaning of words.

Psychologically acceptable communication, if the communication goals of the participants are carried out in accordance with the motives that determine these goals, and if it is carried out using such methods that cause a feeling of dissatisfaction to the partners.

Since communication is an interaction of at least two people, difficulties in its process (called subjective) can be created by one participant or both immediately. And their result, as a rule, is not the achievement of the goal, but a complete or partial lack of motivation or the desired result in activities that serve communication. The psychological reasons for this can be: unrealistic goals, insufficient assessment of the partner, his abilities and interests, misinterpretation of one's own capabilities and misunderstanding of the nature of the partner's assessment and relationship, partner using this method of dealing with

In the study of communication difficulties, there is a risk of conveying their diversity only to discomfort associated with difficulties caused by poor interaction techniques or weak development of socio-prospective functions. In fact, this problem has a global character and covers all aspects of communication. Communication difficulties can also arise due to the fact that the participants belong to different age groups. The result of this is a rejection of their life experiences, which affects not only their existing image in the world - nature, society, people, their attitude towards them, but also certain behaviors in basic life situations. The difference in the life experiences of representatives of different age groups related to communication is expressed by the equal development and manifestation of cognitive processes in communication with another person, the nature of unequal reserves and experiences, and the equal wealth of behavior.

Analyzing the difficulties associated with communication age, it is necessary to take into account the psychological characteristics of each age group and change how they appear as a child, teenager, young man, girl, girl, adult men and women, elderly. The level of development of mental processes specific to each age and the relationship between personality traits and characteristics specific to interacting individuals, such as empathy, decentralization, reflection, identification, and the ability to understand another person using intuition should be paid attention to.

Difficulties in pedagogical communication.

Other difficulties of communication stand out from the point of view of pedagogical psychology. In pedagogy, for a long time, the situation "without any education required" was established. However, for some reason, many teachers believe that the implementation of this thesis implies an authoritarian (object-object) leadership style of students.

Observing the activities of teachers usually shows that they are using spontaneous, borrowed methods reinforced in school to communicate with children. One of the negative consequences of such borrowing is the "line of alienation", that is, the emergence of tension between the teacher and the student, the teacher's own behavior, actions, evaluations, the positive feedback of the student. inability to control his interest in limi. According to researchers, from 60 to 70% of children studied by teachers, with whom there is "alienation" in the relationship, have signs of the disease in advance. Usually, these children are not suitable for educational activities, staying at school becomes a burden for them, intimacy increases, motor and intellectual activity decreases, and there is emotional isolation. Depending on the breakdown of professional communication techniques, researchers identified the following groups of teachers:

- ❖ do not realize alienation towards the student, rejection of the student, situational behavior prevails;
- ❖ alienation is recognized, signs of rejection are isolated, negative evaluations are dominated, and positive outcomes are deliberately sought;
- ❖ alienation is manifested as a way of protecting the personality of the teacher, the behavior of students intentionally leads to violation of the established order and requirements of the teacher.

This group of teachers is distinguished by their status, the desire to avoid comments from the administration, and the concern to introduce strict requirements by negatively evaluating the child's personality and his close surroundings.

"line of alienation" is recognized by the teacher as a professional sign. Almost 60% of teachers see it as a means to achieve discipline and obedience from the first days, 20-25% - to achieve, to show their knowledge, superiority, and only 15-25% the concept of "loving children" related to, their reception they come to the teacher, to feel individuality and uniqueness, to develop activities and ensure free acceptance of norms and rules, all the diversity of school life

Of course, the nature of the psychological difficulties of communication changes with the improvement of the teacher's pedagogical skills. The difficulties of pedagogical communication can be grouped into three main groups: informational, regulatory, and affective. Information difficulties help to report something, to express one's opinion, to clarify, to add, to continue an answer, to finish a thought, to start an offer, to start a conversation, to "give a tone", which requires monosyllabic, predictable answers "narrow" is manifested in formulating questions and answering "broad", problematic creative questions.

Regulatory difficulties are associated with the inability to motivate students. Difficulties in the implementation of affective functions include confirming the words of students, agreeing with them, emphasizing the correctness of language design, correctness of statements, good behavior, boasting for active work, not agreeing with a particular opinion, He is not able to complain about the mistake made, to respond negatively to the violation of discipline.

The severity of these difficulties is determined by the degree of the teacher's tendency to project his states and mental characteristics onto the students. If the teacher lacks the qualities of empathy, decentralization, identification, reflection, communication with him will take the form of formal communication, and students will have a deformation of the development of the emotional sphere. Dissatisfaction of the most important basic need for

private and confidential communication by adults is one of the reasons for the emotional balance of children's responses to others, and it was found that their tendency to aggressive, destructive behavior appears. This also applies to the family if it deprives the child of sincere and loving communication at the level of sincere-trust. E. Pronina and A. S. Spivakovskaya proved that different forms of family interaction are manifested in specific signs of the child's separation from school, in particular, in the sphere of communication with teachers and peers. At the same time, scientists, the abundance of close communication with the child leads to infantilism. Communication difficulties in which the socio-psychological factor prevails can be divided into a separate group.

In addition, there are specific psychological difficulties of communication that often arise between the official and unofficial leaders of the group, and there is always a feeling of jealousy and competition behind them. Difficulties of a socio-psychological origin are people interacting with groups of different social and ethnic origin, membership in warring groups or significantly different in their orientation. includes barriers that appear between.

One of the difficulties of the species in question may arise due to the poor knowledge of a specific language, which is typical of the general language with which the representative needs to communicate. It is not a colloquial language, but a language with which students have been communicating for a long time, or a language formed in this society, etc.

A special type of communication difficulties can be analyzed from the perspective of work psychology. It is known that in many activities it is impossible to work without human interference. And for the successful implementation of this activity, their performers must necessarily cooperate. For this, they must know each other's rights and obligations, and the knowledge of one participant should not be too different from the knowledge of other participants.

For example, when a teacher and a student interact, they usually act according to the rights and obligations assigned to each of them. However, this is not always the case in life. For example, the behavior of the teacher may not be consistent with the reference created in the student. In the eyes of the student, the lack of professional qualifications of the teacher, his formal attitude towards the process and the results of his work may cause psychological difficulties in their communication.

A certain group of communication difficulties between people appears in cases under the jurisdiction of legal psychology. Legal psychology pays special attention to the study of communication difficulties in the process of mutual cooperation of juvenile offenders. The works of domestic and foreign authors show that there are two main forms of disorder in the behavior of difficult teenagers. The first is the socialized form of antisocial behavior. Such teenagers are not characterized by emotional disorders in communication with people, outwardly they easily adapt to any social norms, forms of communication are friendly, have a positive effect on communication. However, this allows them to commit crimes against other people. Having a normal communication style for socially normal people, they do not consider another person as a value.

The second form is poorly socialized. Such teenagers are in constant conflict with others, they are aggressive towards others, not only to fear, but also to their peers. This is expressed in direct aggression or avoidance of communication in the process of communication. The crimes of such teenagers are characterized by cruelty, sadism, and greed.

Of particular interest are the difficulties considered on the basis of individual differences. Research has shown that communication breaks down differently depending on the personality traits of the participants. These personality traits are, in particular, egocentrism. Being strongly focused on himself, his personality, point of view, thoughts, goals, experience, a person cannot perceive another subject, his thought and idea. A person's egocentric orientation is manifested in emotions and behavior.

Emotionally, it manifests itself in indifference to other people's feelings and experiences. From the point of view of behavior - in the form of coordinated actions with a partner. Two types of egocentric orientation were identified: egocentrism as a desire to think from one's own point of view and egoism as a tendency to talk about oneself.

The symptoms of children with communication difficulties include a complex of labile, sensitive, asthenoneurotic features, which indicates their characteristic over-responsibility. In need of friendly communication, they cannot do it because of their inherent shyness and shyness. Initially, they make a very limited, cold, limited impression, which makes it difficult to communicate with others. At the personal level, these people found a high level of anxiety, emotional instability, high self-control of behavior, external manifestations. In addition, a high level of self-denial, self-deprecation was noted. In the survey, they talk about isolation, introversion, shyness, drug addiction, conformism. Their "I" image includes parameters such as low personal and social self-esteem. In addition to the low level of activity and the ability of the "I" to change, this structure of the image of the "I" leads to the fact that a person is closed to feel new experiences that can change his behavior and communication style, and communicative activity continues to produce less effective forms.

Another type of communication difficulties is associated with shyness - a personality trait that occurs in certain situations and is manifested in informal communication and neuropsychiatric stress and psychological discomfort. Shy children are not a homogeneous group in their personal and communicative characteristics. Among them are unadapted (especially shy and schizoid individuals) and adapted (shy).

A special form of difficulty in communicating with others is experienced by individuals suffering from logoneurosis. Research has shown that each of them has its own low-level complex, which begins with a deep dissatisfaction with claims in the field of communication, which disrupts the relationship of a logoneurotic person to other parties. Patients with other mental illnesses, as well as patients suffering from various physical ailments, have specific communication difficulties.

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